

DESIGN OF INTEGRATED MECHATRONIC MACHINES

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ABSTRACT

This article describes the methods of removal of intermediate transducers used in the design of machines of integrated mechatronic systems and their advantages, problems in the application process and ways to overcome them.

Introduction. It is a field of engineering dedicated to multidisciplinary research on the creation of mechatronic, electrical and mechanical systems. For the search for solutions, combinations of different industries are mixed into criteria that can implement high-quality combined processes.[7]

When innovative projects are implemented where different professional alternatives are mixed in the search for a solution, we can say that mechatronic engineering exists. It is a concept based on a combination of occupations that work together.

These areas are achieved in the fields of information technology, electronics, telecommunications and engineering. The

idea is to look for faster and more efficient solutions in industries in which the actions of products, services and systems are involved.[6]

Consequently, the term can be defined as a science that performs the processes by which complex machines and equipment are created, serving to simplify and facilitate human life in practice. The combination of different professional directions determines the level of work and the results are optimal.

Mechatronics is one of the brightest examples of directing science, knowledge and experience to the service of common goals. However, in order to achieve the practical development of the concept, it is necessary to harmonize and shed its parts.

Literature review. The development and current state of the history of mechanical electronics, which dates back to earlier investigations of mechatronics in 1936, has since begun to bear its first fruits. Thanks to Alan Turing, an engineer who started implementing cybernetic type projects.

Various methods of integration have been developed in the design of integrated aggregates of mechatronics. This article discusses how to remove intermediate modifiers and interfaces. These methods can be used alone or in combination with other methods, as they are used at different stages of design. Of course, synergy is widely used in mechatronics. The use of synergy contributes to the rapid development of mechatron modules and their penetration into many areas. Below we will look at ways to remove intermediate converters and interfaces in the design of mechatronic systems.[8]

How to remove intermediate converters and interfaces. The goal of this integration method is to minimize the structural complexity of mechatronic modules by removing intermediate variables. In the design, at least one intermediate block and the corresponding interfaces are removed from the traditional structure. At the same time, its input and output parameters and

the functional changes made by the mechatronic module in general are preserved. This goal can be achieved in the second stage of the design of mechatronic systems, ie in the synthesis of modules.

To design methodologically correct, it is necessary to consider the functional structure of the mechatronic system (MT). A functional view of the MT with certain input and output parameters (as a black box model) is shown. The main functional function of the mechatronic system is to translate information about the movement program into the targeted controlled movement of its final link.[2]

Research Methodology. The motion program can be provided by a high-level computer or by a human operator in the remote control. Controlled movement is performed using the links of the mechanical device, and the final link - the working body interacts with the external environment. During movement, the mechanical link is affected by external forces from the objects being machined (for example, shear forces during grinding and milling operations, contact forces and torques during robot assembly). Feedback is required to assess the state of the system and the external environment in real time.

Additional functions such as reconfiguring the system, signaling and data exchange with other process equipment, and self-diagnostics must also be performed for its efficient and reliable operation. But it is precisely in the external environment that the main task that determines the behavior of the mechatronic system is the precise execution of a given functional movement.

The functional appearance of the mechatronic module in the form of a "black box" includes two data inputs (motion program and feedback), additional mechanical input (reaction forces of the external environment) and one output - targeted mechanical motion. Therefore, in general, the functional scheme of the mechatronic module can be built as an information-mechanical transducer.

An external energy source is required to make mechatronic information-mechanical changes. At the current stage of development of mechatronics, mainly electricity sources are used.[9]

Electricity is only a form of intermediate energy between input data and output mechanical motion. Thus, electricity is not the only energy source to perform its primary function. Of course, other types of energy sources can be used in mechatronic systems for intermediate transformations and should be considered as an alternative at the conceptual design stage.

Analysis and results. The choice of the physical nature of the intermediate variables is determined by the technical feasibility of the variables, the basic requirements and application characteristics.[4]

The following converters are widely used in mechatronic modules:

- The most efficient hydraulic converters in machines designed to

operate under heavy loads, primarily due to their high relative capacity;

- very simple, reliable and high-speed pneumatic converters;

- Chemical modifiers are used mainly in the bioregulations, similar to the muscles of living organisms;

- Combined converters based on energy processes of different physical nature.

Of the seven basic converters mentioned above, three are monoenergetic (information, electrical, and mechanical converters), and their input and output variables are of the same physical nature.

The other four have a dual nature because the input and output parameters have different physical natures. [1] This group includes information-electrical and electromechanical transducers located in the direct chain of the functional model, as well as electrical-information and mechanical-information transducers located in the feedback chain.

The structural model of a mechatronic module (MM) should reflect the composition of its elements and the relationship between them. In the theory of automatic control, it is accepted to create structural models in the form of block diagrams. The links are usually rectangular in shape, indicating the input and output parameters as well as the transmission functions.[5]

The structural model of the electric drive includes the following elements:

- computer motion control device, the functional function of which is to change information (digital signal processing, digital tuning, calculation of control movements, exchange of information with external devices);
- digital-to-analog converter

(DAC) that performs the information-electrical conversion function;

- Power converter, usually consisting of a power amplifier, pulse width modulator (PWM) and a three-phase inverter (for asynchronous motors);
- a controlled electric motor an electromechanical converter;
- a mechanical device that performs a given controlled action and a working body that interacts with an external object;
- feedback device that provides information on voltage and current in the converter;
- feedback sensors (status, speed) that perform the function of mechanical- information exchange;[10]
- Interface devices shown in the block diagram as I 0-I 8.

Depending on the physical nature of the input and output parameters, the interface units can be a mechanical or intelligent converter. Examples of mechanical interfaces are transmissions and transmissions that connect to a mechanical

device motor (I4 interface) and feedback sensors (I7, I8).

Conclusion. Comparing the functional model of the mechatronic module and the structural model of the traditional electric drive, we can conclude that the total number of basic and interface units in the electric drive is significantly higher than the number of functional changes. In other words, there are many structural elements in traditional electric drive. [3] The presence of redundant blocks leads to a decrease in the reliability and accuracy of the technical system, an increase in its overall size and mass, as well as cost performance. This method can significantly reduce the cost of the product and increase the reliability of the work, radically simplify the mechanical design of the module by loading the feedback function on electronic and computer devices. In fact, in this case, the method of eliminating intermediate converters is combined with the third integration method, which aims to expand the functions of smart devices in mechatronic

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